

JUSTIFICATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS AND COMPLEX DIAGNOSIS OF THE DYSFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Received: 16 March 2020 Revised and Accepted: 16 June 2020

Abstract – The incidence of TMJ diseases is quite significant and, according to some literature sources, ranges from 65 to 90.7% [9]. The spread of functional disorders of TMJ and masticatory muscles is affected by the age of the patients, their living conditions and lifestyle, the state of their masticatory apparatus and other factors [5,7,8].

Key words: pathology of the temporomandibular joint, masticatory apparatus, dentoalveolar anomalies, psychoemotional disorders.

I. Introduction

Signs of the pathology of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) begin to be seen in patients from the age of 14. In children and adolescents of a younger age with dentoalveolar anomalies TMJ, cases of initial signs of joint function deviation are single, with the exception of systemic diseases [2,6,18,25].

Diseases of the TMJ and chewing muscles can lead to impaired breathing, chewing, and speech formation, cause psychoemotional disorders and, as a result, cause disability and a deterioration in the quality of life (QOL) of a person [17,10,12,23]. A number of research work is noted in DVA, symptoms of TMJ appear [18,21,28], and other authors identify a relationship between the functional state of TMJ and certain types of occlusion [1,16,26].

Considering the pathogenetic mechanisms of the disease, the role of abnormal bite types in the process of changing the architecture of the TMJ articular surfaces and the topographic relationship of its elements has been proved, which, according to the authors, can be the main reason for the development of articulation dysfunction [4,20].

II. Literature review

Numerous publications of recent years indicate the high importance of psychosomatic factors in the occurrence of pain syndrome dysfunction (PSD) of the TMJ [13,14]. Most often, it leads to a violation of the function of the neuromuscular mechanism that controls and regulates movements in the TMJ. Practical monitoring of the symptom complex of TMJ dysfunction allows us to characterize the course of this disease as progressive, which can lead, as the disease develops, to irreversible organic changes in the joint [20,24]. Moreover, patients with TMJ dysfunction seek help from various specialists, among which: an otorhinolaryngologist, neuropathologist, psychiatrist, therapist, surgeon and other specialists who have insufficient experience in diagnosing this pathology [3,11]. Diagnosis of TMJ pathology is ineffective due to the fact that not all specialists have sufficient qualifications, on the one hand, and not all patients want to be cured, on the other.

III. Analysis

The combination of these factors does not contribute to the formation of a unified approach in the diagnosis of this pathology, and also causes difficulties in the treatment of patients [22]. It should be noted that the issues of etiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis, clinic of organ dysfunction and TMJ function to date, remain not fully resolved. The high and increasing prevalence of this pathology, late reversal and untimely diagnosis confirm the relevance of developing affordable methods for prenosological assessment of TMJ, early diagnosis of TMJ pathology and correction of the patient's diagnostic route with identification of risk factors.

The aim of the study was to determine the importance of the interdisciplinary relationship of the dentist orthopedist for the comprehensive diagnosis of children and adolescents with TMJ pathologies.

Materials and research methods. 300 patients were examined, including 145 patients with TMJ pathologies, also pain in the primary and secondary PSD TMJs, the main group - MG), and 155 patients examined without any

TMJ pathologies (control group - CG); of the total number examined, 130 boys (43.33%) and 170 girls (56.66), in compliance with all ethical principles of medical research involving a person, adopted by the Helsinki Declaration of students in secondary schools and colleges, as well as visiting a dentist in the department “ Orthopedic dentistry "BukhMI and regional children's and adult dental clinics in Bukhara (table No. 1).

Table 1
The group of children examined by gender and age, n = 300

quantity \ Age		Total		Girls		Boys	
		quantity	in%	quantity	in %	quantity	in %
6-9 years old 67/22,33%	MG	25	8,33%	13	4,33%	12	4,06%
	CG	42	14%	22	7,33%	20	6,66%
10-13 years old 100/33,3%	MG	52	17,33%	30	10%	22	7,33%
	CG	48	16%	24	8%	24	8%
14-18 years old 133/44,3%	MG	68	22,66%	41	13,66%	27	9,0%
	CG	65	21,66%	40	13,33%	25	8,33%
Total 300/100%	MG	145	48,33%	84	28%	61	20,33%
	CG	155	51,66%	86	28,66%	69	23%

The survey was divided into two phases; at the first, they collected and analyzed information received directly from the patient, listened to his subjective opinion about how the disease began and how it developed; on the second, objective symptoms were established, a detailed examination of the patient was carried out. In order to increase the diagnostic efficiency, a unified coding map of the clinical examination was developed, which includes a list of signs of TMJ dysfunction. All results of the obtained data on measurements and assessments by the conditions of the oral cavity (OC) were recorded on floppy disks for subsequent statistical processing.

Dental examination and examination was carried out with a standard set of dental instruments according to the generally accepted scheme: interrogation, examination, examination of MMOC, teeth and dentitions, periodontal tissues, chewing muscles and TMJ organs. It was ascertained whether earlier orthodontic treatment was carried out, surgical interventions in the MHF, what complaints the patient presents to this person to examine facial facies. When evaluating the face in profile, attention was paid to the shape, angle size and relief of the lower jaw body edge (l / j). When assessing proportions in full view, attention was paid to symmetry, vertical proportionality of the face, symmetry of the teeth relative to the midline, the nature of the closing of the lips and the severity of the folds. Evaluated the smoothness of movements l / j when opening and closing the mouth, tour of the articular heads, their location in the articular cavities. The closure of the dentition in the sagittal, vertical and transverse directions was evaluated. When stating the functional part of the diagnosis, dynamic tests were performed (respiratory, speech, swallowing). According to indications, clinical functional tests were performed. The orthodontic diagnosis was made in accordance with the classifications of Engle and L. Persina. According to the testimonies, orthopantomograms and magnetic resonance imaging studies were performed selectively (according to S. A. Gafforov on methodological recommendations [3].

In order to study and analyze the medical and social aspects of the course of the TMJ, the objective examination data were entered into the map “Objective examination data for the TMJ and the masticatory muscles” and the Verbal Descriptor Scale (VDP) was used to score pain sensations (VDP) - [Similarities in pain descriptions ..., 1990]; questionnaire KЖSF-36 (Medical Out comes Study Short Form, Health Status Survey) consisting of 36 questions, in order to study the characteristics of socio-psychological adaptation and personality traits that are associated with TMJ pathologies, the diagnosis of socio-psychological adaptation of personality of K. Rogers and R was carried out Daimon [15].

The resulting materials calculated the group arithmetic mean (M) and standard error of the mean (m), which are presented in the final tables. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statisticaver program. 7.0

The results obtained and their discussion. According to the results of examinations among children and adolescents with TMJ pathologies, a medial bite was detected in 17 patients (25.0 ± 0.10) aged 14–18 years, in 16 children and adolescents - 30.7 ± 0.03 at the age of 10–13 years in the MG. Children with TMJ pathology often had crowded teeth. Crowding of teeth l / j was found in 8.0 ± 0.12 cases in children aged 6–9 years, in children in the exhaust gas 10–13 years old - 11.5 ± 0.03; and in 11.8 ± 0.13 cases in children aged 14–18 years. It was found that

the crowding of teeth u / j per hour was relatively high in 12.0 ± 0.10 cases in exhaustives of 6–9 years, 15.4 ± 0.03 in exhaust gases of 10–13 years and in 13.2 ± 0.12 cases in groups of 14–18 years old (table No. 2).

Table number 2.

Occurred bite forms in examined children and adolescents from 6 to 18 years

Bite	Age	CG = 155 healthy children and youths Only 24 physiol. bite -15.5%						MG = 145 children and youths with pathological TMJ. Only 145 patol. bite -100%					
		6-9 years old; n= 42		10-13 years old n= 48		14-18 years old n= 65		6-9 years old n= 25		10-13 years old n= 52		14-18 years old n= 68	
		number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Distal		-	0	-	0	-	0	3	12,0	3	5,7	1	1,4
Back		-	0	1	0,2	1	0,15	3	12,0	4	7,7	6	8,8
Open		-	0	-	0	-	0	3	12,0	3	5,7	8	11,8
Deep		-	0	2	0,42	3	0,46	2	8,0	4	7,7	6	8,8
Bipognatic		1	0,24	3	0,62	-	-	1	4,0	1	1,9	3	4,4
Protrusion		-	0	-	0	-	0	2	8,0	5	9,6	5	7,3
Crowded l / j		1	0,24	2	0,42	3	0,46	2	8,0	6	11,5	8	11,8
Crowded military unit u / j		-	0	2	0,42	2	0,3	3	12,0	8	15,4	9	13,2
Cross		-	0	-	0	2	0,3	1	4,0	2	3,8	5	7,3
Medial		-	0	-	0	1	0,15	5	20,0	16	30,7	17	25,0
Total		2	0,48	10	2,08	12	1,84	25	100	52	100	68	100

Defects in the dentition with TMJ pathology were observed in 81.37 ± 0.13 children, and in 118 children of the EXHAUST. Of these, the majority of infraocclusions were detected in the group of children aged 14-18 years old 82.3 ± 0.06 . In the CG, 3.2 ± 0.11 diastema of the jaw was observed and 10.3 ± 0.05 in the MG with pathology of the TMJ. In MG, the highest diastema defect rate was observed in the group of children aged 10–13 years. Supraocclusion was also observed in 15.5 ± 0.05 children in the MG 10-13 years old. Dystopia of the teeth was not found in children in the CG, a total of 4.8 ± 0.05 was observed in the MG, of which 5.8 ± 0.11 was observed in the group of children aged 10-13 years (table №.3).

Table No. 3.

Occurred defects of the dentition in the examined children and youths of children from 6 to 18 years

Bite	Age	Bite 155 healthy children and youths						145 children and youths with TMJ pathologies									
		155 children		6-9 years old; n= 42		10-13 years old n= 48		14-18 years old n= 65		145 children		6-9 years old n= 25		10-13 years old n= 52		14-18 years old; n= 68	
		amount	%	amount	%	amount	%	amount	%	amount	%	amount	%	amount	%	amount	%
Dystopia		-	-	0	0	-	0	-	0	7/4,8	4	16,0	3	5,8	-	0	
Infraocclusion		4/2,6	1	2,4	1	2,1	2	3,1	88/60,7	12	4,8	20	38,5	56	82,3		
Diastema		5/3,2	1	2,4	2	4,2	2	3,1	15/10,3	1	4,0	8	15,4	6	8,8		
Supraocclusion		6/3,9	-	0	4	8,33	2	3,1	8/5,5	1	4,0	7	13,5	-	0		

Total	15/ 9,7%	2	4,8	7	14,6	6	9,23	118/ 81,37%	18	72,0	38	73,1	62	91,2
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As a result of a polyprofessional clinical examination by specialists, objectification of dysfunctional muscle disorders, a clinical diagnosis of the study group of 48 patients of boys from 14-18 years of age who complained of PSD TMJ was performed.

In turn, 1 - the group (from the MG) of the patients was divided into two subgroups ("A" and "B"), differing in the representation in each of them of functional disorders of the TMJ chewing muscles, data on which were obtained using the Clinical Index scale TMJ dysfunction "[Helkimo M., 1976].

Subgroup "A" consisted of patients with a Helkimo index of more than 5 points, and group "B" - with a Helkimo index of up to 5 points.

Table No. 4.
Clinical groups of examined patients, depending on complaints

Patient groups		ICD-10		Number of patients / group encoding
Group I (symptomatic PST index - over 24)	subgroup "A" (Helkimo dysfunction index - 5-20)	K07.6	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	N = 18 K-F
	subgroup "B" (Helkimo dysfunction index - up to 5)	K07.6	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	N = 18 O-F
Group II (symptomatic PST index - up to 24)		K07.6 dysfunction index Helkimo - 5-20	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	N = 12 K-0

Subgroup A included patients (18 patients; 37.5%), whose clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease made it possible to attribute their complaints to those characteristic of mixed manifestations of the disease, namely, neurological disorders with prevailing pronounced muscle-tonic diseases in the clinical picture of the disease and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (K07.6), combined with somatoform disorders (F45.0), manifested in the form of psycho-vegetative disorders (F45.3); chronic somatoform pain disorder (F45.4); psycho-vegetative disorders with severe dysfunction of other organs and systems, including "grinding of teeth": (F45.8) (according to ICD-10).

Subgroup "B" included patients (18 patients; 37.5%), whose clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease made it possible to attribute their complaints to those characteristic for somatoform disorders, attributable to F45.3, F45.4 and 45.8, but distinguished by the absence neurological disorders proper, namely: pronounced muscle-tonic and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (K07.6).

The clinical 2-group consisted of patients (12 people; 25%), the clinical features of the disease of which were characterized by pronounced neurological symptom complexes, namely, muscular-tonic and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (K07.6). At the same time, the result of their clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease allowed them to reject the presence of any somatophore symptomatic manifestations.

In general, this general nature of complaints required differential diagnosis and differentiation of the diagnosis of TMJ PSD from TMJ arthropathy, trigeminal neuralgia and other types of chronic facial pain, as well as osteochondrosis of the cervical spine (CS) and other head and neck diseases accompanied by pain and impairment movements. During a clinical examination of patients, localized areas were identified which were indicated by the studied patients: upper part of the face; TMJ area; facial muscles and chewing muscles; face area.

Pain in the upper part of the face: At the time of examination, one-sided spilled pain in the upper half of the face without clear localization complained of 7 people (14.58%). The average intensity on the VDP pain scale was 3.8 ± 0.9 points. Of these, 3 people (6.25%) bothered unilateral pain with irradiation. The average intensity on the VDP pain scale turned out to be 4.2 ± 1.1 points.

IV. Discussion

It should be noted that this symptom bothered patients during clinical diagnosis, they mainly complained of a somatoform nature (group 1). Complaints of severity and pain in the neck were noted by 10 patients (20.84%) with pain in the face and the presence of a concomitant spinal disease in the form of osteochondrosis in the short-term history of osteochondrosis. The average intensity on the CS pain scale in them turned out to be 2.4 ± 2.5 points. In patients with facial pain, the following pain phenomena of muscle-tonic disorders were identified: pain and discomfort in the TT region and in the areas of reflected muscle pain m. masseter, m. temporalis, m. Pterygoideus medialis / lateralis.

Complaints of a burning sensation in the face region were noted by 2 people (4.2%), and unpleasant sensations in the form of local numbness and decreased sensitivity of the facial skin were presented by 5 patients (10.4%) with traumatic damage to the branches of n. Trigeminus. The average intensity of burning sensation as a variant of pain sensation on the VDP scale turned out to be 3.5 ± 0.5 points. A group of patients with TMJ PSD was characterized by complaints of burning sensation in the oral cavity (OC) at the time of examination and in a short history.

Separately considered pain in the mucous membrane of the mouth, gums and tongue. Also, burning in the tongue bothered 3 people (6.2%), and burning in the mouth (without clear localization, but more often one-sided) - 6 people (12.5%).

The average intensity of a burning sensation in the area of the mucous membrane of the mouth and tongue as a variant of pain sensation on the VDP scale was 4.1 ± 2.1 points. This symptom must be attributed to somatized pain disorders, because the nature of the burning sensation, described as long-term, low-intensity, not responding to treatment with local methods, is characteristic of such disorders.

An analysis of the results of an objective examination of patients with TMJ PSD by the Hotelling's Trace method, showing the representation of their complaints in each of the examined groups and subgroups, revealed the absence of statistical significance of differences ($p = 0.7$).

In the studied groups and subgroups, the data regarding the mobility of n / h differed (HelkimoM., 1976)], presented in Figure No.1

Fig. No. 1. The nature of the amplitude of the opening of the mouth of patients with TMJ PSD. Evaluation of the average indicators for this parameter found the following differences in the groups and subgroups of the examined patients.

The limitation of the amplitude of the opening of the mouth was not detected in patients of the subgroup "B" of the 1st group, and a small number of observations were noted in the 2nd group. For the most part, patients with limited opening of the mouth made up the subgroup "A" of the 1st group.

Thus, limiting the opening of the mouth is an important diagnostic criterion for patients of the subgroup "A", included in the 1-group, characterized by the largest proportion of complaints presented by them, and is not observed in patients of the subgroup "B" of the 1-group.

Our assessment of pain in the TMJ according to the VDP scale for the entire population of examined patients is given in Table. №5.

Table № 5
The severity of pain presented in the complaints

Localization of pain	Nature of pain	VDP scale, average mark
Pain in the upper half faces	One-sided spilled pain in the face	$3,8 \pm 0,9$

and areas of CS	Unilateral pain in the face with irradiation	4,2±1,0
	Heaviness and pain in the neck	2,4±2,5
	Local daily pain in the upper face	4,5±1,2
	Burning sensation in the face	3,5±0,5
	Local diseases of the facial skin by type hyperesthesia	3,0±1,2
	Burning “in the mouth”, “in the tongue”	4,1±2,1
TMJ pain	Local pain in the TMJ	5,2±2,3
	Spilled pain in the TMJ	4,5±1,8
	Paroxysmal pain in the TMJ	5,2 ±1,6
	Constant pain in the TMJ area of aching nature	4,1±2,6
	TMJ pain associated with exercise	4,8±3,2
	TMJ pain at night	3,1±1,5
Localization of sensations in the mouth and upper and lower jaw	Chewing pain and tension	4,1±2,1
	Chewing pain during prolonged chewing	5,2±1,5
	Pain and tension in the facial muscles of the face	3,8±1,8

As you can see, the overall indicators on the VDP scale were within the "moderate" pain, regardless of its location. At the same time, a subjective assessment of the severity of pain in various parts of the face according to the results of the VDP scale is presented in the following figure No. 2.

Figure number 2. The severity of pain in various parts of the face according to VDP

As you can see, the greatest intensity of pain occurred in the masticatory muscles during chewing and loading - more than 5 points according to VDP, as well as the paroxysmal nature of pain in the TMJ or local pain in the TMJ - more than 5 points according to VDP.

Chewing muscle electromyography (EMG) was performed in 48 patients from 68 examined adolescents (70.58%). Analysis of the obtained EMG allowed us to identify 4 types of EMG; in 12 patients (17.64%) there was no change in EMG and it was characterized by symmetrical tonic activity; in 18 patients (26.5%) there were pathological changes in EMG; in 6 (8.8%) patients these changes were characterized by asymmetry of the same muscles on the right and left, “bioelectric silence”, short-term single bursts, “reflex” rigidity in response to the load.

In 12 patients (17.6%), EMG changes were characterized by the presence of “bioelectric silence” with a simultaneous hypersynchronous electromyogram. Such patients complained of unpleasant sensations of tightening

in the face, especially during a conversation, in the cold. The pain in this case was most often detected at rest, and the extension of the affected muscle significantly increased it. At the same time, in 24 patients (35.3%) - the largest number among those who underwent EMG examination - EMG changes were characterized by "bioelectrical silence", tremor-like or volley-shaped electromyogram.

Thus, according to the results of the study, it was possible to establish that a significant proportion of patients with TMJ have a facial hypertension, the nature and severity of which require a directed diagnostic assessment. The obtained results on the QOL SF-36 questionnaire comparison in the subscales of SF-36 by multivariate multivariate analysis revealed the statistical significance of QOL for each group and subgroup of patients ($p = 0.003$). This fact allows us to conclude that it is important to study QOL of patients with TMJ PSD in adolescents and adults. The relationship of the duration of the disease with QOL has not been established ($p =$ from 0.2-0.9). Consideration of the total indicators for the SF-36 subscales in the studied groups and subgroups revealed pronounced differences in their QOL (Figure№ 3).

The average values for SF-36 subscales and their comparison with the average norm, physical activity and, accordingly, working capacity in the studied groups was not reduced. The data obtained are consistent with clinical observations showing that most patients remained healthy and did not resort to frequent use of sick leave, freeing them from work.

Appendix: ** - $p \leq 0.01$ - statistically significant, * - $p \leq 0.05$, ~ - at the trend level

An analysis of the results shows that the overall vital activity in patients of subgroup "A" of the 1st group is significantly reduced due to somatic health problems ($p = 0.004$): these patients, while maintaining their working capacity, significantly limited their overall vital activity.

According to the results of the questionnaire by C. Rogers and R. Daimon, psychological testing and assessment of patient complaints, three adaptation groups were identified; "Healthy" (22.6%) - a group with a high ability to adapt; A group with an average ability to adapt (40.5%) and a group with a low ability to adapt (44.8%) and, accordingly, a high risk of maladaptation. The results of socio - psychological adaptation by the method of multivariate multivariate analysis, showing the significance of the presented data group in clinically selected groups and subgroups of the examined patients, demonstrated their statistical significance ($p = 0.014$). This fact allows us to conclude that it is important to study the socio-psychological adaptation of patients with TMJ PSD in the integrative diagnosis of this suffering and the complex of therapeutic measures associated with it (table No. 6).

Table № 6

Diagnostics of the socio-psychological adaptation of personality according to the methodology of C. Rogers and R. Daimon

Scale	Average values	Median	Normal zone	Standard deviation	Standard error Wed mean

Adaptability	122,52	129,00	68-136	29,75	3,87
Maladaptation *	38,77	18,00	68-136	43,76	5,70
Deceit- *	8,48	7,00	18-36	8,14	1,06
Falsehood + *	7,67	9,00	18-36	7,31	0,95
Self Acceptance *	22,31	29,00	22-42	20,37	2,65
Self aversion *	6,90	0,00	18-28	8,95	1,17
Acceptance of others *	14,22	18,00	12-24	14,12	1,84
Rejection of others *	8,90	5,00	14-28	9,93	1,29
Emotional comfort *	10,40	0,00	14-28	11,18	1,46
Emotional discomfort *	8,24	4,00	14-28	11,01	1,43
Internal control *	27,78	45,00	26-52	27,51	3,58
External control *	8,62	4,00	18-36	10,59	1,38
Domination *	3,85	0,00	6-12	5,02	0,65
Statement *	8,13	0,00	12-24	9,35	1,22
Escapism (avoiding problems) *	5,21	0,00	10-20	6,46	0,84

Note: * - distribution is significantly different from normal.

Using the U Mann – Whitney test, intergroup differences were identified. The average data on the scales of the method are presented in figure No. 4

Figure number 4.
Intergroup differences in the socio-psychological adaptation of personality (C. Rogers and R. Daimon)
 (cf. data in groups, “norm”)

Appendix; ** - $p \leq 0.01$ statistically significant, * - $p \leq 0.05$, ~ - at the trend level

As you can see, the “acceptance of others” (norm from 12 to 24 points) in patients of the subgroup “A” of the 1st group turned out to be higher than in patients of the subgroup “B” of the 1st group ($p < 0.003$, average 16.5 points). This means that patients with mixed (neurological and somatoform) symptoms are much less likely to “accept others” than patients only with somatoform symptoms, who more often establish “warm, good relations with others”, treating people favorably, knowing how to get along with them and considering themselves sociable and open to others.

At the same time, “self-rejection” in patients of subgroup “A” of group I turned out to be lower than in patients of subgroup “B” of group I ($p < 0.002$; 5.7 points). This means that patients with mixed symptoms are much less likely to “accept themselves” than patients only with somatoform symptoms, that is, they have low self-esteem, they often “doubt that someone of the opposite sex may like you”; consider that in their personality “there is nothing in which they can express themselves, show their individuality, their Self”; that they are “worthy of contempt”; say that they often “make decisions and immediately change them”, while despising themselves for such lack of will” (norm from 12 to 24 points) in patients of subgroup “A” of group I turned out to be higher than in patients of subgroup “B” Group I ($p < 0.001$; 13.5 points).

This means that patients with mixed (neurological and somatoform) symptoms are less dependent on the opinions of other significant individuals than patients with only somatoform symptoms. They are less likely to note their dependence on other people's rules, are able to make independent decisions and act at their discretion. The indicator “escapism” or “flight into fantasy” (norm from 10 to 20 points) in patients of subgroup “A” of the 1st group turned out to be higher than in patients of the 2nd group ($p < 0.04$; 6.7 points).

The following various factors serve as grounds for judgments about maladaptation: low acceptance of others; low level of self-acceptance; emotional discomfort, which has a very different nature; externalism, i.e., a strong dependence on other people; desire for dominance.

Thus, on the basis of an analysis of the responses of the studied patients, it can be concluded that patients who encounter problems consider DVA diseases to be a very significant factor, which largely determines the success of their social functioning.

Violations in the orofacial area, potentially visible by other people, form phobic tension associated with this circumstance, due to the “unaesthetic” nature of the suffering and the possibility of changing diction, thereby complicating full social contact and changing the self-awareness and self-esteem of patients in a negative way.

V. Conclusion

In the diagnosis of TMJ pathology in adolescents, the following clinical, dental, morphological and dental symptoms and phenomena took place:

- 1) the presence of pain with predominantly unilateral irradiation;
- 2) unilateral localization of hyperesthesia in the face;

- 3) the presence of local and diffuse pain in the TMJ;
- 4) the presence of pain in the TMJ area associated with the load on it that occurred during an exacerbation or subsiding exacerbation of the TMJ PSD;
- 5) the presence of pain and discomfort in the area of chewing muscles (due to muscle-tonic syndrome) with the presence / absence of local pain;
- 6) difficulty in chewing and the occurrence of pain with it;
- 7) a feeling of "tightening" and discomfort in the face;
- 8) limiting the amplitude of the opening of the mouth (due to increased muscle tone, muscle spasm);
- 9) the displacement of the lower jaw when opening the mouth (due to dysfunctional disorders of the masticatory muscles);
- 10) the presence of "noise" phenomena ("crunching", "clicking" in the joint) associated with the tension of the joint-ligamentous apparatus. The psychological factor that distinguishes the studied groups of examined patients was the nature of their QOL. With somatoform inclusions, a slight decrease in the quality of life indicators was found due to unpleasant "subjective sensations", an indicator of the state of "general health at present, vital activity due to emotional problems, and also by subscales " vitality " and " social activity " (p = 0,000) .

A study of the intrapsychic parameters that ensure the social adaptation of patients with TMJ PSD according to the "socio-psychological adaptation" scale [15] revealed a negative effect on them of somatoform inclusions, most pronounced with a mixed genesis of suffering. This was manifested in them in a low level of acceptance of other persons, as well as a low level of self-acceptance, the presence of emotional discomfort, which has a very different nature, as well as externality, i.e., a strong dependence on other people.

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